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Industry-Partners' Assessment and Feedback: Input to BPIHS BriGHTEST Café

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Abstract

This study intended to measure the assessment and feedback of Industry-Partners on Work Immersion during the School Year 2023-2024. The respondents of the study were the supervisors of Work Immersion Industry-Partners. The study made use quantitative method in measuring the assessment of the industry-partners and qualitative design on discussing its feedback. On the level of performance of the students as revealed in the assessment of the supervisors or partner-industry with respect to different competencies in Work Immersion, students garnered an exemplary performance, however it is noticeable that competencies such as communication skills and customer service skills should be given an attention on upskilling. Hereafter, students exhibit positive results on their performance on the Work Immersion as assessed by the Industry-Partners. However, supervisors from the industry-partners highly recommend to expose the students in a real-life school laboratory facility that can increase their engagement and customer service skills.

Keywords: Industry-Partners' Assessment, Feedback, Work Immersion.

Introduction

According to Republic Act 10533, also known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, Section 5, "the Department of Education shall adhere to the following standards and principles in developing the enhanced basic education curriculum: (d) the curriculum shall be localized and global; and (h) the curriculum shall be flexible enough to enable all The production and development of locally produced teaching materials will be encouraged, with approval devolving to the regional and division education units."

The law requires the department to develop instructional materials that are aligned with the needs of the basic education curriculum, and it encourages every teacher to localize or contextualize instructional materials that will best suit each learner. This prompts the researcher, who is also a classroom teacher, to create and implement a Localized Work Immersion Workbook that is best suited for all students.

One concerning issue is that some employers remain hesitant to hire K-12 graduates, despite the fact that the implementation of the K-12 program has not significantly increased their hiring prospects. A jobs portal reported on Jobstreet, which tracked job postings and the results of an employer survey, found that 35% of respondents were not ready to hire graduates of the extended basic education program. Forty-one percent of respondents said they were undecided about hiring K-12 graduates, while only 24 percent said "yes". Employers, however, "can only claim to have some knowledge" of the program based on a self-assessment, according to Job Street (2018).

The majority of employers reiterated that attitude/work ethic remained the most important hiring criteria, followed by communications skills and practical thinking, which replaced 2016's field of study and salary preferences. Willingness to learn, personal grooming, and teamwork were rated as the best qualities of recent graduates, while leadership skills were among those that require the most improvement.

The aforementioned qualities, characteristics, and traits are the top priority and focus competencies of the work immersion subject, prompting the researcher, a classroom teacher, to undergo and collect the Industry-Partners' assessment and feedback on the performance of students who participated in the job simulation in order to address and intensify the needs of honing the skills of K-12 students before they graduate.

The researcher was motivated to focus on this type of study in order to measure the assessment and gather feedback from industry partners to determine whether the curriculum met industry standards and requirements and could be adjusted accordingly.

Action Research Questions

This study aimed to gather the assessment and feedback of the Industry-Partners on the performance of the students during their Work Immersion. Specifically, the study sought answers the following questions:

1. What is the assessment of the industry-partners on the performance of the students with respect to the following competencies:

- 1.1 resume writing;

1.2 application letter writing;

1.3 job interview;

1.4 work ethics

1.5 communication skills; and

1.6 customer service skills?

2. What is the feedback of the Industry-Partners on the performance of the students during their Work Immersion?

Proposed Innovation, Intervention and Strategy

The study would like to measure the assessment and gathered the feedback of the Industry-Partners on the performance of the students during their work simulation under the learning area of Work Immersion for Grade 12 Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track Home Economics Strand at Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School. The study was conducted during Third and Fourth Quarter of the school year 2023-2024.

Truly, the critical characteristics of learning are the key to achieve authenticity and life-long learning. It must meet the level of the learners and not of that the teacher wanted to achieve for them. When students feel involvement and relevance on the matter at hand, they tend to become more involved in the discussion.

It is parallel with the study of Concepcion (2021), he learned that exposing students into a real-world aspect would help them to put the theory into realization.

And with this, teacher-researcher decided to craft a Project Proposal based on the assessment and feedbacks of the Industry-Partners. Utilizing actual work scenario facilities are recommended in helping learners improve their performance.

Methodology

Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information

The study focused on the assessment and feedback of the Industry-Partners on the performance of the students during their Work Immersion.

The participant of this study were those Grade 12 students taking Work Immersion subject under Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track Home Economics Strand.

The assessment and feedback from the Supervisor/ Industry Partners on the performance of the students on their immersion were considered.

Data Gathering Methods

The researcher used descriptive research design, since the researcher gather the needed data from the assessment and feedback of the industry-partners. It is also focused on describing and summarizing the characteristics of a particular population or phenomenon.

Feedback on the performance of the students from the Industry-Partners were considered for the inputs on how the curriculum fit the demand on the industry.

Data Analysis Plan

The data were analyzed using the following tool and/or technique:

To determine on how supervisors/ industry partners assess the performance of the students with respect to the cited competencies, mean and standard deviation were used.

To determine the feedback of the industry-partners with regard to the performance of the students, qualitative discussion was utilized.

Results and Discussion

Assessment of the Industry-Partners on the Performance of the Students with Respect to Resume, Application Letter, Job Interview, Work Ethics, Communication Skills, and Customer Service Skills

Table 1 shows the level of performance on the performance of the students in their work immersion as evaluated by the supervisors or industry partners with respect to resume, application letter, job interview, work ethics, communication skills, and customer service skills.

Table 1

Assessment of the Supervisors or Industry Partners on the Performance of the Experimental and Control Group with Respect to the Competencies

	Mean	VI
Resume	9.12	O
Application Letter	9.27	O
Job Interview	19.45	O
Work Ethics	18.48	O
Communication Skills	14.45	O
Customer Service Skills	11.48	O
Total	82.25	O

Legend: O- Outstanding

It can be seen on the table that on the level of performance of the students as evaluated by the Supervisors or Industry Partners with respect to cited competencies, obtained O or Outstanding on the mentioned competencies.

Also, it can be reflected that the students acquired the needed said competencies of the subject.

It appears that the students garnered a grand mean score of 82.25. The findings proved that upon the assessment of the Industry-Partners, students was able to exhibit a commendable performance however, it was needed an attention to attain an increase in the value of assessment.

This supports the study of Espiritu (2021) that a real-life laboratory facility is an

aid to progress the level of performance of the students evident in the increase in the result of its performance evaluation sheet.

Feedback of Industry Partners on the Performance of the Students on their Work Immersion

As assembled from the collected feedbacks coming from the industry-partner, most on the supervisors affirmed that the students in terms of documents such as application letter and resume exhibits a good level of performance.

However, they reiterated that the school or the curriculum should help the students to be more ready in the workplace by providing them a more realistic and industry-based school training and exposure. This will greatly help them to be more confident on dealing and engaging with customers.

It conforms in the study of Santa Cruz (2021), a laboratory facility obviously leads to a more organize and systematic way of teaching-learning process thus a remarkable progress is visible on the learners.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, students exhibit positive results on their performance on the Work Immersion as assessed by the Industry-Partners. However, supervisors from the industry-partners highly recommend to expose the students in a real-life school laboratory facility that can increase their engagement and customer service skills.

Recommendations

In the light of the foregoing results of the study, the following recommendations were hereby forwarded:

1. Teachers who handle the same subject may continue to partner with the industry to check and balance their teaching and learning practices.
2. Teachers may craft a Project Proposal on the realization of the inputs of the industry-partners on increasing the performance of the said students.
3. Another study on the performance of the students on work immersion may be conducted considering other variables.

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